

FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE AND INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCIES AS THE CORE OF OFFICERS' SUCCESSFUL OPERATION IN INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation. *Foreign language proficiency and intercultural competence considered to be valuable and advantageous skills for the service members of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The Ministry of Defence of Ukraine has recognized the significance of foreign language communicative skills for its staff. Knowledge of the most commonly used foreign language, which is English for Ukraine's military partner countries, and understanding of foreign culture is critically important for the successful implementation of international military activities. The thesis is that an understanding of language and knowledge of culture are critically important individual characteristics of modern officers involved in international military activities. Officers' successful functioning in international operations depends on their readiness to perform duties in multicultural and foreign language speaking environment.*

Since language is an integral part of culture, learning a foreign language means that cultural awareness is acquired at the same time. Consequently, foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies are interrelated abilities which supposed to be formed and developed simultaneously. The Armed Forces of Ukraine must educate and sustain a language trained and culturally oriented officers' corps in order to remain prepared to face the challenges of future international military activities. Thus, a modernization of the curricula of the Ukrainian higher military education institutions has to be made in order to focus English learning on the target foreign culture and developing future officers' foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies.

Keywords: *communicative competence, intercultural competence, foreign language, international operations, military education and training.*

Generally, the whole military sector can be described as a large multinational, multilingual, and multicultural company comprising diversity of ethnoses, motives, values, norms, etc. At the global and at the local levels, which often means respectively international and national ones, it is a workplace where service members are involved into individual professional interaction, institutional advancement and achievement, and where they show and exert national and international power (Orna-Montesinos, 2013, p. 99). From the other side, it is well known, and historically proven that military operations by their nature can only be successful when people involved in them are able

to communicate and work together.

Beyond doubt, the ability of the Armed Forces of Ukraine to operate effectively together with its allies and partner nations is fundamental to promoting to regional and global peace and security. Today's complex challenges steadily foster different countries to work with or even through others: enabling allied and partner capabilities, building joint capacities and developing mechanisms to share the possible risks and responsibilities.

In modern security sector interoperability is considered to be one of the key elements which help all the stakeholders to work effectively together in joint operations. For example, NATO defines interoperability as “the ability to act together coherently, effectively and efficiently to achieve Allied tactical, operational and strategic objectives” (NATO AAP-06, 2021).

However, ensuring interoperability with partners in foreign language speaking and multicultural environment often proves to be a complicated and severe challenge, basically due to the insufficient foreign language proficiency of the personnel. As English language has undoubtedly become the lingua franca in the military and its predominance as the preferred language of the personal and professional development is widely confirmed (Orna-Montesinos, 2013), in context of this study foreign language generally refers to English.

Many experts agree that interoperability is supported primarily by the ability of service members of different countries to interact, connect and communicate, exchange information and data. Therefore, developing communicative skills, enhancing foreign language proficiency and intercultural communication abilities, as well as other associated with them professional and individual competencies of servicemen can be considered to be a key issue for the success of international military activities.

The Ministry of Defence of Ukraine considers the knowledge of English as an integral part of a new officer's corps military culture based on Euro-Atlantic values and principles. As well the Ukrainian higher military command determines the foreign language proficiency of servicemen as one of the main aspects of achieving interoperability with NATO structures (The Road Map of Improving Language Training, 2021). Nowadays English language learning is mandatory in the system of professional military education in the Armed Forces of Ukraine.

As for NATO, presently linguistic interoperability is admitted as the core component of effective international communication of military personnel and NATO Standardization Agreement 6001 provides NATO forces with a table describing language proficiency levels of the commonly-recognized language proficiency skills: “listening”, “speaking”, “reading”, and “writing” (STANAG 6001, 2014).

At the same time, there are authoritative scientists in the field of Behavioral and Social Sciences who advocate for the adoption of a “culture and language strategy” for the military education and training involving not only the development of language proficiency, but culture awareness and expertise as well (Abbe, 2008). In their studies the concept “culture” has numerous meanings and is often defined as a pattern of beliefs,

value systems, rituals, behaviors and practices that have an impact on the individual and the organization. Therefore, individual's roles in an organization must be considered in capacity building efforts. Individuals whose norms are different, even if the nation's government structures, technology base, and human technical capacity are similar, may not readily accept solutions and concepts that rest on Western norms (Morgan, 2002).

Actually, foreign language teaching at Ukrainian higher military education institutions is professionally oriented and integrated into the special disciplines. The process of teaching English is designed accordingly to cadets' needs which are determined by their future military occupation (Jaros, 2018). The actual main objective of English learning at higher military education institutions is acquiring foreign language communicative skills and professionally oriented foreign language communicative competence by future officers. However, presently, it seems that there is no strong emphasis on the incorporation of cultural awareness programs, teaching modules, etc. into the curricula, and designated intercultural competence development efforts are not sufficiently implemented as well. In fact, intercultural training is not delivered during military education and training, except specialized courses for service members selected for participation in peacekeeping operations, multinational exercises and other international military cooperation activities.

Additionally, modern pedagogy concepts "intercultural communication", "foreign language communicative competence", "intercultural competence" and some other terms relevant to this study have different and sometimes controversial definitions which sometimes can vary due to the peculiar features of the language used for the explanation of their meaning. Thus, in the context of the presented research, it appears appropriate to provide the most common scientific approaches and views on the issues being considered.

First of all, it worth mentioning that asserting that "culture" is an area of knowledge or expertise separable from language, and that we might attain knowledge of the former without the latter, is likely unsupportable proposition. The two are of course intimately related, and can only be effectively learned together. Attempts to separate the two produce an overly academic, highly generalized type of knowledge that may hardly find a practical implementation. This approach has largely been discredited in the broader field of anthropology (LeVine, 2001).

Academics tend to agree that foreign language and cultural education are complementary; an appreciation of culture facilitates foreign language competency, and speaking a foreign language facilitates the in-depth understanding of culture (Joint Doctrine Note 1/09, 2009, p. 1–3). However, there is some debate as to whether each of the two competencies is "essential" for learning the other (Stringer, 2009). According to Patrick R. Moran, author of *Teaching Culture: Perspectives in Practice*, it is not necessary to master a language in order to build cultural competency; however, learning a language can serve as a "critical step" in understanding culture. Moran says: "Making the effort to understand another language, listening, negotiating meanings, all these facets of communication through language demonstrate respect, which allows the learner to engage in an authentic inquiry into a culture. As the process builds, relationships emerge.

And relationships become the foundation for meaningful cross-cultural engagements” (Moran, 2001).

Some believe that the teaching of culture should be an integral part of foreign language instruction. For example, in an article titled “The Importance of Teaching Culture in the Foreign Language Classroom,” Dimitrios Thanasoulas argues that cultural awareness must be viewed as “something more than merely a compartmentalized subject within the foreign language curriculum.” Instead, says Thanasoulas, culture must “inhabit” the class-room and “undergird every language activity” (Thanasoulas, 2001).

But, according to UK Joint Doctrine Note 1/9, culture does facilitate the use of language, and “linguistic skills facilitate the gaining and exploitation of cultural knowledge.” However, while linguistic ability does not guarantee knowledge of culture, “all personnel can benefit from enhanced cultural capability.” According to this perspective, “It is possible for a relatively high level of cultural capability to be achieved with limited language ability. However, to be an effective linguist, a reasonable level of cultural capability is required in order to maximize the opportunities presented through direct engagement” (Joint Doctrine Note 1/09, 2009, p. 15–16). Colonel Brett Lewis, author of “Developing Soldier Competency,” agrees, but for more practical reasons. He argues that foreign language proficiency is not an essential component of cultural competency because “not all soldiers have the aptitude to learn another language,” too much time is required to develop and maintain proficiency, and secondary options, including translators or technology in the form of “near-universal language translations” on hand-held devices or laptops, are usually available (Lewis, 2006).

The US Army’s Training and Doctrine Command (TRADOC) Culture Center defines culture as a “dynamic social system,” containing the values, beliefs, behaviors, and norms of a “specific group, organization, society or other collectivity” learned, shared, internalized, and changeable by all members of the society (Culture Education and Training Strategy for the U.S. Army, 2007).

At West Point, the newly created Center for Languages, Cultures, and Regional Studies takes a broader approach. While accepting TRADOC’s fundamental definition of culture, the Center for Languages, Cultures, and Regional Studies looks at language, culture, and the knowledge of regional dynamics as vitally interrelated and equally important aspects of intercultural effectiveness. Such effectiveness requires a skill set that encompasses language study and the cultural awareness it engenders, as well as cross-cultural competence through language and other cultural training, and knowledge of regional dynamics and how such knowledge relates intrinsically to both the culture and language (Wolfel, 2008).

Actually, starting as early as 1967, Robert Lado stated that “a central objective in the process of teaching and learning foreign languages should be the development of the competence to use the acquired foreign language in the target cultural environment” (Lado, 1967, p. 68). However, neither the audio-lingual, nor the communicative-pragmatic approach, which dominated the process of teaching/learning foreign languages in the 1970s and 1980s, did not address this objective, continuing to be restricted to

the linguistic aspect and the speech acts, considered to be universal in using a foreign language (Niculescu et al., 2019).

Currently, in foreign language teaching and learning the concept of intercultural communication has become a dominant one, supposing a rethinking of the whole process. Intercultural communication is seen by scholars as “communication between [...] two people from two obviously different groups” (Apeltauer, 1997, p. 17); a situation of interaction when interpersonal communication is conducted between members of different cultural groups (Litters, 1995, p. 20). Some other authors emphasize the fact that intercultural communication studies the contact between individuals, and not between the cultures they are affiliated to.

While being defined in different ways this concept has two essential features which are determined by most scholars:

1) intercultural communication is considered as a process of interaction between people who are aware of their cultural differences;

2) communication is interpersonal, direct, unmediated.

Scientist-educators note that in the didactics of foreign languages, the concept of intercultural communication refers mainly to the concrete teaching and learning situation, which is defined as an encounter between the culture of origin and the target culture. The transition from the culture of origin to the target culture is often fraught with stress as it involves a split from the familiar cultural matrix regarding the identity of the individual. Brandusa-Oana Niculescu and other researchers suggest that this difficulty can be overcome through the development of the intercultural competence. It can be realized through the achievement of several objectives, which are progressively distributed over three levels:

3) perception of own culture, without any reflection on it, awareness of pertaining to a certain cultural environment, as well as of the cultural differences between individuals;

4) differentiation of prejudices and revision of stereotypes about oneself, which involves the affective component in the process of understanding the foreign cultural environment;

5) understanding of the behavior specific to a foreign cultural environment, which also implies the social-pragmatic component. (Niculescu et al., 2019).

Intercultural communication skills are actions and behaviors that are intentionally repeatable and goal-oriented during interaction (Spitzberg, 2000). Such skills use appropriate and effective processes to successfully navigate an intercultural encounter in order to achieve the desired outcome. These culture-general competencies can be effectively taught and developed. Those that are most relevant to officers have been condensed into the following eight foundational skills of intercultural communication:

1. Interaction management
2. Impression management
3. Self-monitoring
4. Perceptual acuity
5. Paralanguage use and perception

6. Nonverbal communication

7. Active listening techniques

8. Communication styles

To summarize, interaction management is the effective and appropriate use of conversational turn-taking, information-gaining strategies, and topic choice “based on a reasonably accurate assessment of the needs and desires of others” (Ruben, 1976, p. 341). Interaction skills are goal-oriented behaviors enacted while communicating with an individual or group (Spitzberg, 2003) and are strongly affected by cultural preferences for direct or indirect messages as well as an orientation toward task or relational outcomes.

Impression management is defined as deliberate and motivated self-presentation and assumes that a basic motivation of individuals is to be viewed favorably by others (Goffman, 1959).

Effective impression management across cultures requires self-monitoring, which is the ability to detect appropriateness of social behaviors and self-presentation in response to situational constraints and to adjust our behaviors to fit the situation (Chen & Starosta, 1997).

Perceptual acuity is the flip side to self-monitoring. Defined as “attention to and accurate detection of various aspects of the environment” (Montagliani & Giacalone, 1998, p.601), perceptual acuity is necessary for a communicator to accurately recognize how one is perceived by others in an interaction. Accuracy will often hinge on a conversational partner’s verbal, nonverbal and paralinguistic cues.

Communication style is defined as: “The way in which we communicate, a pattern of verbal and nonverbal behaviors that comprises our preferred ways of giving and receiving information in a specific situation. If the message content is the what, and the communicators are the who, then communication style is the how” (Saphiere, Mikk, & DeVries, 2005, p. 5). Difference in communication style preferences are often conveyed via paralanguage (how a message is delivered through rate of speech, volume, word emphasis, intonation, and silence), via nonverbal communication (conveying messages through the use of touch, space, time, and body movement) and via active listening practices (culturally variable feedback preferences used to communicate understanding to a speaker).

Presently, researchers suggest service members to apply the set of guidelines designed to improve intercultural communication skills:

- being aware of your own culture;
- being other-oriented;
- being curious in dealing with different cultures;
- tolerating ambiguity;
- being behaviorally flexible;
- being emphatic;
- getting into contact with people coming from different cultures (Niculescu &

Obilișteanu, 2015).

Studying competencies, in particular foreign language communicative competence

and intercultural competence, which are related to intercultural communication and its subsets, scientists concluded the following:

- communicative competence has the crucial role for military specialists who should not only have a good command of the basic language, but also have information about specific areas of vocabulary (military translation, medical and legal vocabulary); have knowledge in the field of military terminology; have knowledge about the country (in particular, about the political system, religion, culture, history); know the nature of combined action; know the organizational and staffing structure of both their troops and enemy troops; be ready for translation in difficult combat and climatic conditions (Romanenko, 2016).

- foreign language communicative competence refers to learner's ability to use communicative strategies and mechanisms which are necessary for providing efficient interaction (Nikolaeva, 2011);

- the content of foreign language communicative competence includes the knowledge about communication under different circumstances with different communicants, and also verbal and nonverbal basics of interaction, ability of its efficient usage in the specific communication acting as an addressant and as a addressee (Batevych, 2009).

Recently the innovative modern method of forming foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies of future officers was created and proposed for implementation by Ukrainian researchers Mykhaylo Kozyar, Lidiia Nanivska and other. This method consists of several successive stages, including:

- adaptive stage, when promoting background for successful development of foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies of cadets is being created;

- reproductive stage, intended on formation of readiness to use foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies in future professional activities;

- productive and creative stage, designed for the active creative application of intercultural and communicative competencies;

- reflexive stage, which comprises development and practical application of cadets' skills of self-analysis and self-assessment of their own intercultural and communicative competencies levels, as well as for determining proper ways of further development;

- control and evaluation stage, for external evaluation of the level of cadets' foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies (Kozyar & other, 2020).

Definitely, learning and understanding a foreign language and culture is not something that happens quickly, it requires a significant investment of time and educational efforts. However, in the Armed Forces of Ukraine issues of intercultural communication training and forming foreign language competence are particularly novel. Therefore, it seems to be early to sum up and analyze the current national expertise in officers' foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies formation and development.

Conclusions. Training and developing foreign language and intercultural communication skills is the cornerstone of military communication as manifested in

international environment.

The necessity of foreign language and intercultural training is directly linked to officers' actual professional capacities, and overall success of international operations, missions, or other multilateral activities. Language proficiency provides officers the ability to go beyond simple observation and equips them with the skills to successfully interact with foreign counterparts and understand operationally relevant cultural realities. Without a strong focus on foreign language training and proper cultural training, the effectiveness of officers' operation in international environment will be limited.

Accordingly, effective operation in international environment has to be provided and facilitated by foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies of the military personnel.

Outside of the goal of achieving higher capabilities in international activities and multinational operations, development of foreign language communicative and intercultural competencies has the ability to create a more erudite and understanding officer overall which, in general, is definitely beneficial for the Armed Forces.

Suggested further research encompasses experimental verification of the implemented and newly proposed models of formation of future officers' foreign language communicative and cultural competencies at higher military education institutions and military education units of higher education institutions of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine; finding and examining effective approaches to specialized professional training and development of servicemen readiness to operate in international environment, and other intercultural communication related studies.

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